

TEACHER'S VIEWS ON 'TEACHER TRAINING SYSTEM IN TURKEY'

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Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the views of the teachers on teacher training system in Turkey, and it was conducted using the case study design, which is one of the qualitative research designs. The working group of the study consisted of 55 teachers in total, who voluntarily participate in the research. These teachers are serving in one of Turkey's provinces and its town centers connected with one of the seven geographical regions, the Eastern Anatolia Region. The data of the study were collected using the interview technique. In the research, the interview form approach that is one of the types of interview was used. The content analysis technique was used to analyse the collected data through the interview form. As a result of the research, it has been found that participant teachers generally have negative opinions about teacher training system in Turkey. The teachers say that there is no national policy on teacher training system in Turkey. According to them, there is weak co-ordination between the teachers training institutions and the institutions that employ teachers. They stated that changes to the entry system should be made to the institutions that train teachers. These teachers claim that teacher training programs must also be updated, and even the in-service trainings contribute to the professional development of teachers, it is necessary to carry out studies for the enhancement of the qualifications of these trainings. Finally, they stated that the teacher training system with the pedagogical formation education certificate program should be terminated.

Keywords: teacher training in Turkey, pedagogical formation education certificate program, faculty of education

1. Introduction

Rapid changes and developments experienced in science and technology in the 21st century, which we call information age, have led to a competition atmosphere between

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countries in terms of producing information. This competition has enabled the development of an educational system based on knowledge production. One of the aims of the education system in the information age is to educate learners who have the desired qualities in finding, producing and presenting information. The importance of the education of the teachers who will train them has begun to be emphasized for the education of those who have these qualifications. Therefore, continuous evaluation of the teacher training system in all aspects is important for the training of individuals who have the desired qualities required by today and tomorrow. In this context, in this study, teacher training methods in Turkish education system will be examined, today's teacher training system will be scrutinized with the eye of the teachers who have graduated from this system and have begun to work and teachers' opinions and suggestions regarding the system will be taken. It is expected that the results obtained from the research will be shed light on the works to be done, in order to increase the qualifications of teachers in our country.

2. Literature Review

2.1 From Past to Present Teacher Training Studies in Turkish Education System

2.1.1 Teacher Training to Primary Schools

The first teacher types that make formal education studies in the history of Turkish education are the teachers who teach in Ottoman primary school and the professors who teach in madrasahs. These teachers and professors are trained in the madrasah system and their general characteristics are as follows: They only specialize in the field of religious sciences and usually give religious education; their teaching methods based on taking notes, memorizing information and interpreting old books. Except these methods, they do not use any explicit teaching methods (Ergün, 1987). It can be said that, the roots of teacher education in the contemporary sense in Turkey comes from the Tanzimat Reform Era. These teachers are who know how to teach, not just what to teach (Yıldırım & Vural, 2014).

During the Tanzimat Reform Era, in 1848, in order to educate teachers to Ottoman high schools, the first teacher school was opened with the name of Darülmualimin as a male teacher school. According to the regulation prepared by the director of the institution, Ahmet Cevat Efendi, students who know enough to understand Arabic will be taken by exam to Darülmualimin and they will be trained for 3 years. In addition, the first course to be taught in school will be "Teaching and Learning Methods". Graduates will be assigned with an examination according to their success grades and they will be retained in Darülmualimîn, by paying their salary, for the reinforcement of their knowledge until they start to work (Akyüz, 2006). In addition to Darülmualimîn, who taught only men until 1869, at that time, a school of teachers called "Darülmualimat" was opened for girls. These two schools continued to study and teach until 1924 (Korkmaz, Bağçeci, Meşe, Ünsal, 2013).

During the Republic period, with the Tevhid-i Tedrisat law, the name of Darülmualimin has become "Male Teaching School" and the name of Darülmualimat has become "Female Teaching School". At least, since 1935, the name of these schools has become only "Teaching School" (Akyüz, 2015). In 1926, two types of teacher training schools were opened, which names were "Elementary Teaching Schools" and "Village Teaching Schools" in order to train elementary school teachers (MEB, 1995, s.15). Elementary teaching schools provided 5 years of education in 1924 on primary school education, after the 1932-33 school year, they have become teacher schools that provide 6 years of education (Akyüz, 2015, p.381-382). The village teaching schools were established to take the children raised in the village and give them general, professional and local informations in a 3-year education after the primary school education and make them teacher (Koçer, 1994). However, after trying 5-6 years the village teaching schools, in 1932-1933 these schools were closed due to the fact that they were inadequate (Dilek, 2016). In those years, the Ministry of National Education (MEB) also applied practical solutions to supply the needs of village teachers. In 1936, the peasant youth who had been served as military officers or sergeants and ex-serviced were trained in short courses and had been employed in village schools with the title of "trainer" (Özkan, 2016). As a continuation of the various experiments of the 1930's (such as Education Dormitories, Village Teacher Courses) in 1940, Village Institutes established which gives education for 5 years after the primary school in order to train teachers for village primary schools (Dursunoğlu, 2003). According to Institute laws, healthy and talented peasant children who finish village primary schools will be selected to these schools, after completing a 5-year education and training course at the institute they will graduate and will teach in villages for 20 years. Those who do not complete 20 years of compulsory service will no longer be public officer and will pay compensation. In the institute that established for the development of the village, it is aimed to integration of training and production and to train graduates to be both technicians and teachers (Kaplan, 2002). The Village Institutes, which were closed in 1953, have been reorganized under the name of the 6-years "Elementary School". With this arrangement, the implementation of teacher training from different schools to village primary schools and urban primary schools has come to an end, and standardization has been achieved in the structures and programs of the institutions that train primary school teachers (High Education Board, 1998). Since then, these schools have continued to receive mainly primary school graduate students, and together with the other 3-years Primary Schools, program integrity is provided at the high school level (Dursunoğlu, 2003).

In 1973, with the enactment of the Basic Law on National Education No. 1739 it is stipulated that teachers should be provided with higher education regardless of their level of education and two-year "Education Institutes" have been established within the Primary Schools in order to train classroom teachers for this purpose. Primary Education Schools, which do not have educational institutes contain in themselves, have been transformed into teacher high schools (Akyüz, 2015, p.383). With this law, all higher education institutions are transformed into universities. As a result, 2-year

training institutes from teacher training institutions that affiliated to the Ministry of National Education, have been transformed into Education High Schools and four-year Higher Education Schools have also been transformed into faculties of education (Aras & Sözen, 2012).

2.1.2 Teacher Training to Secondary Schools

In the era when the Republic was founded, secondary education was based on two sources of teacher training. These were schools that educate secondary school teachers and institutions that train branch teachers to high schools (Demircioğlu, 2008, p.227). In 1926-27 school year, in order to train "Secondary School Turkish Lesson Teacher" a 2-year "Secondary Teaching School" was established in Konya and then this school was transferred to Ankara. After that, new departments have been added to this school and the name has been changed to "Gazi Teaching School and Education Board" in 1929 (Güneş, 2016). The students, who were taken to Gazi Teaching School and Education Board after the high school education, were able to become secondary school teachers. The first trainings were two years and then they become 3-year education. This institution, which educated secondary school teachers, had been transformed into "Education Institute" (3-year Education Institute) after 1946. Since 1978-79 school years, it had been named as "Higher Teacher Education School". These schools are organized in such a way that they can train high school teachers. On July 20, 1982, the duration of education is determined as 4 years and these schools transformed into faculties of education and affiliated to existing or newly established universities (Akyüz, 2015, p.387).

2.1.3 Teacher Training to High Schools

The foundations of secondary school teacher training, which is the second level of secondary education, based on the Ottoman Empire's Darülmualimins. Dârülmualimîn has been developed over time and turned into an institution called as "Dârülmualimîn-i Âliye", which contains the parts that train primary, secondary and high school teachers in itself. In 1891, the "Âli" part of the institution was transformed into a high school, which is a teacher training school for modern day high school students (Eşme, 2003). With the opening of Istanbul University in 1933, Teacher training at high school level was transferred to the "Istanbul Higher Teacher School" (Demircioğlu, 2008, p.228). A group of students, who graduated from the university and entered the university's faculties of science and letters, is selected to this school by an exam and they were educated by MEB for 4 years as free boarding students, including high school teachers in various branches (Kavcar, 1982). In addition to the field education, the pre-service teachers also took pedagogical lessons. And also, these students have been subjected to compulsory service because of free and boarding study (Katoğlu, 1997). Istanbul Higher Teacher School remained the only institution training teachers for high schools and their equivalents until 1959 (Öztürk, 1999). After 1959, the number of Teacher School was increased, while the students who were graduated from Teacher Schools were selected by these schools at the beginning, the succeeding

students from the last year of Teacher School started to be taken in the following years. These institutions, which have produced qualified teachers for many years, were closed on 18 July 1978. (Kavcar, 1982). After this date, the number of education institutions that have raised branch teachers has been increased to 4 years and their names have been changed to "Higher Teacher School". In 1982, some of the Higher Teachers' Schools were converted into education faculties, and some became colleges of education and connected to existing or newly established universities. In the 1989-90 academic year, the duration of the education colleges was increased to 4 years and in 1992 it was either turned into education faculty or attached to the education faculty as classroom teacher department. (Akyüz, 2015, p.387-389).

2.2 Teacher Training With Pedagogical Formation Education Certificate Program

Since 1982, institution of higher education has assumed the responsibility for teacher training in Turkey. In our country, teachers are trained directly by both education faculties and various faculties such as science literature, science, economics and administrative sciences, health sciences, theology faculty, state conservatory as long as having pedagogical formation education. In this way, the teacher training process began in the 1990s. Towards the end of 1990s, it was seen that education faculties ignored the task of raising teachers to pre-school, classroom and secondary school by taking science and basic researches as a foreground, and causing a significant amount of teacher deficiency (Taneri, 2016). Since that date, various certificate programs have been launched in order to ensure that teachers who do not graduate from education faculties become teachers in order to solve the teacher deficiency (Eraslan & Çakıcı, 2011).

In order to train qualified teachers, the High Education Board initiated the restructuring process of education faculties in 1997 and removed the teaching certificate program which was prepared to train secondary school teachers with the reason of insufficient content and duration and replaced them with non-thesis graduate programs (YÖK, 1998). In 1997 teaching programs for secondary education in accordance with the principle of fulfilling teacher deficiency in all institutions, education faculties started to give 5 years education and to graduate with a non-thesis master's degree. After students have taken their department courses from science faculty, they have completed their last 1 or 1.5 years of education in education faculties (Türkmen, 2012). With the new regulation made by High Education Board (YÖK) in 2010, graduate programs without thesis were abolished and formation training started to be implemented again. Thus, students who are studying in or have graduated from various departments (science, theology, economics and administrative sciences, health sciences, etc.) are allowed to become candidate teachers with the certificates they have received.

Teacher training in our country has become one of the most controversial issues of our education system because of the numerous and important changes made in the course of teacher training in two different ways and the pedagogical formation training certificate program within a short period of time. However, the opinions and suggestions taken from the practitioners of the education system have a great

importance in determining the positive and negative aspects of our teacher training system, in determining the existing problems and solutions. For this reason, working on this project, teachers' opinions and suggestions about teacher training system applied in our country have been tried to be determined. In order to reach this aim, the answer of the question "What are the views of the teachers on the system of teacher training in Turkey" has been tried to be found.

3. Material and Methods

The research was conducted using the case study design from the qualitative research designs. Case study; is an empirical research that examines a contemporary phenomenon in its real-life context, especially if the boundaries between the phenomenon and the context are unclear and multiple sources of evidence are used (Yin, 1984, s. 23).

3.1 Studying Group

The working group of the study consisted of 55 (n=55) teachers in total, who voluntarily participate in the research. These teachers are serving in one of Turkey's provinces and its town centers connected with one of the seven geographical regions, the Eastern Anatolia Region. For the identification of the working group criterion sampling, which is one of the purposeful sampling types, was used. The purpose of the criterion sampling is the study of all situations that supply a set of predetermined criteria (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013, p.140). Criteria for the formation of the study group are participants' educational status, the educational institutions they work for and their years to start pre-service training. All participants must be graduate from faculty of education and have started their pre-service training in the faculty as of 2006-2007 academic year. An attention has been paid to the fact that teachers are also serving in pre-primary, primary, secondary and higher education institutions.

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Study Group

Demographic information		N
Gender	Female	35
	Male	20
Period of service	1-5 years	36
	6-10 years	10
	11-15 years	5
	16-20 years	2
	Over 20 years	2
Field of Study	School teaching	10
	Pre-school teaching	9
	Psychological counseling and guidance	6
	Information Technologies and software	3
	English	4
	Turkish	5
	Religious culture and moral knowledge	3
Mathematics	3	

	Sciences	3
	Elementary mathematics	2
	Physical sciences	2
	Social studies	2
	Literature	3
Organization	Pre-school	9
	Primary school	12
	Secondary school	17
	High school	17

3.2 Data Collection Tools

Data of the study were collected using the interview method. The interview form approach, which is one of the interview methods, was used in the research. Researchers started with literature review on teacher training in the process of preparing interview questions, and then they determined 12 open-ended questions. The prepared questions were examined by 3 field experts and 2 teachers, after necessary corrections were made the final form has been converted into a 7-question interview form. The questions in the form are as follows:

- a) What are your general views on teacher education policies in Turkey?
- b) What are your views on the entrance conditions to the faculties of education?
- c) What are your views about the training programs implemented in the training faculties?
- d) What is your opinion about the duration of education and training in faculty of education?
- e) What are your views about the conditions for assignment to the teaching profession?
- f) What are your opinions about in-service training studies?
- g) What are your views on teacher training with the pedagogical formation education certificate program?

3.3 Data Analysis

For the analysis of collected data through the interview form, content analysis technique is conducted separately by one of the researchers and by an expert. For this purpose, the data were codified, themes were created to collect codes under certain categories and the data were rearranged and defined according to this theme. At the end of the analysis process, the codes that the researcher and the expert agree on, were left as they are. The other codes that the researcher and the expert do not agree on were re-read and discussed by these two coders till provide a consensus. To determine the reliability of the content analysis,

Reliability = Agreement/Agreement + Disagreement

formula, which was proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994), was used. The reliability level of the study was detected as 86% on all questions.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 2 contains the opinions of the teachers who participated in the research. They express their opinion on the question: "What are your general views on teacher education policies in Turkey?"

Table 2: Teacher's General Views on Teacher Education Policies in Turkey

Main categories	Sub-categories	Codes	f	%
The Views on YÖK's Teacher Training Policies	Views on Undergraduate Curriculum	There is not enough in-class activities during undergraduate education	12	19
		School Experience and Teaching Practice courses' credits are inadequate.	12	19
		Teacher training undergraduate programs are not preparatory to the profession.	5	8
		During the undergraduate education, the studies on the development of the technological pedagogical field knowledge in the courses are inadequate.	1	1
	Views on Teacher Qualifications	Qualifications of teachers trained by training faculties do not correspond with the qualifications of the teachers determined by the Ministry of National Education (MEB).	6	9
		Teacher training with pedagogical formation education certificate program weakens teacher qualifications.	5	8
Views on MEB's Teacher Training Policies	Views on Teacher Training Policies	There is no national teacher training policy of MEB.	11	17
		Person in charge of teacher training policies and practices are far from educational problems in Turkey.	2	3
	Views on Teacher Employment	There is no cooperation between MEB and YÖK (High Education Board) on teacher employment.	10	15

According to Table 2, the majority of the participating teachers (47%) expressed their opinions with the category of "Undergraduate Curriculum" that is under the main category of "Views on Teacher Education Policies of High Education Board". Within this sub-category, 46% of the teachers criticized the teacher training undergraduate curriculum in a negative way. They stated that these programs are not preparative for the profession and there are not enough in-class activities in the programs. In addition, they point out that the School Experience and Teaching Practice courses' are provide professional experience, but the credits of these courses are inadequate.

Teacher views in these regard are as follows: "...it is necessary to practice rather than theoretical knowledge while educating teachers. Because teaching is a work that requires experience and universities are not able to provide this experience adequately." (T23); "While educating university students, internship training should be given to university students from the second grade. Because a pre-service teacher who does not have a long-term internship training can experience a lot of troubles when he/she is assigned." (T11); "Unfortunately, the

lessons taught in the course do not work in the professional life it means that programs are not preparatory for Professional life. So, teachers' opinions should be taken and the programs should be organized and renewed according to these opinions." (T40).

In the same main category, within the "Views on Teacher Qualifications" sub-category, 9% (n=6) of teachers stated that there is a difference between the qualifications of MEB for teachers and the training qualifications of YÖK for pre-service teachers. Because of this difference, they stated that new teachers in the profession could have difficulties at various levels in the process of adaptation to the profession. One of the teachers explained his/her opinion on this issue as follows: (T45) *"In faculties teachers are not training according to MEB. There is a discrepancy between the teachers who have been educated and the teachers that MEB wants to create. Especially, in the first years of your profession, you feel this discrepancy more deeply. In time, you adapt to the MEB but the process can be overwhelming."* 8% (n = 5) of the participating teachers criticized the pedagogical formation education certificate program and stated that teacher training process with this program reduced the qualifications of teachers. One of the teachers (T25) criticized the pedagogical formation education certificate program as follows: *"...Some implementations are necessary to improve the quality of teachers. I find it wrong to give pedagogical formation to the graduates of faculty of science and letters. Teaching is a profession that requires important qualifications. It is not right to be assigned to this profession with this inadequate formation courses."*

When the "Views on the Teacher Training Policies of MEB" are examined, 17% of participant teachers (n=11) stated that MEB had no national teacher training policy and its policies changed constantly depending on the government. They also stated that, this situation had a negative effect on teacher qualifications. One of the teachers (T57) explained his/her opinion this issue as follows: *"We should have a good teacher training policy in our country but we should not. This constant change of our policy depends on the government is a big problem. This situation creates a problem on education qualifies of teachers..."*. 3% of the teachers (n=2) stated that there is no teaching experience of the people who responsible for teacher training policies in Turkey and that's another big problem. One of the teachers (T7) explains his/her opinion as follows: *"...the fact that people who prepare politics are really far from the troubles of the field and their training is not in this area increases the inconveniences. I think that we need a minister and practitioners who work in schools"*. In addition, 15% (n = 10) of the participating teachers stated that cooperation between MEB and YÖK is not desirable qualities in terms of teacher employment, they think that more teachers were trained in higher education institutions more than needed and for this reason, they said that the employment of the graduated teachers could not be provided. One of the teachers (T16) considered the teacher training policies in our country in terms of employment problem as follows: *"Since the MEB does not fully agree with YÖK, the employed policy adversely affect pre-service teachers and causing more teachers than needed."*

In the Table 3, there are the results of the analysis of the data obtained from the views of the teachers that participate to the research about the question: *"What are your views on the entrance conditions to the faculties of education?"*

Table 3: Teachers' Views on Entry Requirements to Educational Faculties

Main categories	Sub-categories	Codes	f	%	
Views on Revision of Existing Entry Conditions	Gradual Examination System Must Be Applied	Oral exams that evaluate expression and skill should be applied.	24	27	
		Personality tests should be applied.	17	19	
		Occupational interest tests should be applied.	11	12	
		Teaching proficiency test should be applied.	9	10	
		Psychological tests should be applied.	5	5	
		Values tests should be applied.	2	2	
			Mental health tests should be applied.	2	2
			In the process of high school education, the students who can carry out the teaching profession should be determined and studies should be directed to the profession.	9	10
		Job Orientation Studies Should Be Done	In entrance exams for universities, the minimum passing score must be increased for education faculties.	5	5
			Preferences of the departments should be done at the end of the basic education period taken in the education faculties.	1	1
		School Experience and Teaching Practices courses must be taken to the first year of undergraduate curriculum.	1	1	
	Judicial Control Must Be Done	Security clearance should be made at the entrance to the training faculties.	5	5	
Views on The Adequacy of Existing Entry Conditions	Central Examination Implementation Should Be Continued	The existing conditions for entry into the education faculties are sufficient.	1	1	

As seen in Table 3, participant teachers emphasized the "Gradual Examination System" the most. In this category, 100% of the teachers agreed that central exam points should be included in the admission to faculties of education. However as an additional measure, they also think that pre-service teachers should also be evaluated based on conversational- and skill-based oral tests, personality tests, psychological, mental stability, and ethical assessments. One teacher (T28) remarks "*Pre-service teachers who wish to be admitted to faculties of education should be assessed via interviews. Whether they can express themselves clearly or whether they can convey the ideas should be scrutinized.*"; another remarks (T7) "*We place trust in our teachers by letting them teach our children. There are many who does not have what it takes to be a real teacher. There should be some additional character in addition to written exams*"; (T38) "*Education is a genuinely skill-based occupation. Skill, passion, and success are the essentials for education. Faculties of education teach the teachers who would raise the future of the country. Thus, admissions should be not only based on a single exam but also based on interest and passion for the subject too.*"; (T3) "*Before anything, whoever wants to be a teacher should possess patriotism and compassion for fellow country people, an interest in ownership of the cultural heritage etc. There must be tests in place to evaluate these.*"

According to Table 3, 17% of the teachers (n=16) stated that there is a need for job orientation in the entrance of the faculties of education. 10% (n = 9) of the teachers stated that high school students should be directed to the teaching profession. They also stated that teachers who work in high schools must observe the students (as personal, social, moral, and cognitive) and direct these students to faculties of education. One of the teachers (T28) stated his/her opinion follows as: *“University admission test is definitely not enough. Teachers’ opinions should be taken from high school years. Considering the character, habits, and behaviors of the student, a report should be prepared by the high school teachers that “the student is suitable to be a teacher”.* One of the participant teachers (n=1) made a suggestion about that the efforts to direct the pre-service teacher to the branches of faculty of education should be done at the end of the 2 years theoretical education. One of the teachers (T13) remarks pre-service teachers should make preferences of their branches in the process of the university education. He/She stated that: *“Students should take some basic information in the first and second years and then it is necessary to make orientation studies for students via instructors in order to select branches by participating internships, practice and observation of various departments. I think it would be better. Unfortunately, many teachers in our country do not like their professions.”* In addition, 5% (n=5) of the teachers stated that security clearances should be made at the entrance to the faculties of education. A teacher (n=1) stated that the current conditions for entry into the faculties of education were adequate and there was no need for any additional exams.

Table 4 shows the results of the analysis of the data obtained from the opinions of the participant teachers on the question: *“What are your views about the teaching programs applied in the faculties of education?”*

Table 4: Views on Teaching Programs Applied in Teachers' Education Faculties

Main categories	Sub-categories	Codes	f	%
Views on Revision of the Programs' Content Element	Views on the theory- practice balance of the courses	The theoretical and practical balance of the lessons is not sufficiently achieved.	39	49
		Village life and village schools	3	4
	Suggested courses to be added to the program	Living conditions in regions	2	3
		Scientific studies	2	3
		Special training	1	1
		Painting analysis	1	1
	Views on the content of curriculum	First aid training	1	1
		Diction	1	1
		The content of pedagogical lessons is not functional.	3	4
	Lessons that suggested to be removed from the program	There is no relationship between the lessons.	1	1
Anatomy		2	3	
Views on	Views on	Turkish, Ataturk's Principles and History of Turkish Revolution	1	1
		Weekly course hours of School Experience and Teaching Practices	12	15

Revision of The Programs' Teaching-Learning Element	course hours	courses should be increased		
	Views on teaching methods and techniques used in lessons	The methodologies used in the courses provide professional development.	3	4
Views on the Practitioners of the Programs	Views on the instructor of the course	Instructors are not adequately educated in their professions. Instructors do not have teaching experiences.	6	8
			1	1

When the Table 4 is examined, 49% (n = 39) of the participant teachers in the main category "Views on the Revision of Content Instruction of Teaching Programs", stated that the theoretical and practical balance of the lessons in the programs was not adequately provided and the lessons were mainly theoretically processed. One of the teachers (T7) explains his/her opinion on this issue follows as: *"I think that the current training programs are inadequate. Universities should focus on practices differently than transferring theoretical informations"*. 14% of the teachers said that, some courses should be added to teacher education undergraduate programs like painting analysis (n = 1), scientific studies (n = 2), special training (n = 1), village life and village schools (n =3), diction (n = 1), living conditions in regions (n=2) and first aid training (n=1). 4% of the teachers expressed their opinion as the anatomy course in preschool education branch (n=2) and Turkish and Atatürk's Principles and Revolutions courses which are in the common compulsory courses in all branches of education (n=1) are not necessary and they argued that these courses should be removed from the program. From teachers (T23), *"Universities and internship places are located in city centers but we are appointed to villages. Living in the village is really difficult. Courses about the difficulties in village schools and village life should be added to the program; (T3)"Teachers can live difficulties in adapting to living conditions in the places they have been appointed. For this reason, courses such as living conditions in the regions should be given in the schools"; (T11) "Teachers do not have enough knowledge, especially on doing scientific academic work. A course about this is required."; (T18) "There were lessons that were unnecessary as much as the necessary ones. For example, anatomy. It must be removed from the program."*

According to Table 4, 15% (n = 12) of the participant teachers had expressed their views on the course hours in the main category "Views on revision of the teaching-learning element of the programs", that *"the weekly application hours of school experience and teaching practice lessons were inadequate and these should be augmented"* they had stated. One of teachers had expressed his/her opinion *"I do not find the programs enough, because the internship is inadequate, the lessons we learn are very theoretical. Even if the internship training is a little more, it would be better. I am in favour of internship in different schools for 3 days, not 1 day of the week."*(T22); another teacher also expressed his/her idea *"The training period should be extended to 5 years and only application lesson should be given 4 days a week in school and 1 day in faculty in the senior year. If so, we can better reflect the course contents to the teaching process"*(T16). 4% of the teachers (n=3) stated that the methodology which is used in the lessons contributed to the

improvement of the profession and they expressed a positive opinion about the teaching-learning element of their programs. It is seen that 8% of the teachers (n=6) expressed opinions about the in charge lecturers, the lecturers were not adequately shipshape in the areas of expertise (%8, n=6) and the instructors had no teaching experience (1%, n=1). From teachers (T49) "*Teacher who is in our faculty is insufficient as a teacher how to lecture us, we all learn in private teaching institutions. The instructors are not experienced and well-supported in this regard.*" expressed his/her opinion with these sentences.

Table 5 contains the opinions of teachers about the question "*What is your opinion about the duration of education and training in faculty of education?*"

Table 5: Teachers' Opinions about the Duration of Education in Faculties of Education

Categories	Codes	f	%
Views on Current Education-Training Period	The current period of education is adequate.	22	38
	The current education-training period should be increased.	8	14
	Current theoretical education-training period should be reduced.	1	2
Views on The Necessity of Post Graduate Education	Teachers should be encouraged to apply post-graduate education for professional development.	20	34
	Post-graduate training must be a requirement for being a teacher.	6	10
	Some branches require a post-graduate training to become a teacher.	1	2

According to Table 5, 38% (n=22) of the participant teachers stated that it is sufficient to carry out this profession and the duration of 4 years education in faculty of education and whether or not take the post graduate education should be left to the teachers' preferences. One of the teachers "*I think the duration for education is sufficient. Reducing the duration creates congestion. It will bring out the problem of not being able to concentrate enough. The excess of duration also causes loss of time (T43) "*, explains the view of sufficiency of the duration. While 14% of the participant teachers (n=8) stated that the current education period should be increased to 5 years and in the 5th year, application oriented courses should be included, one of the participants (n=1) stated that the theoretical education is given in the faculties of education should be reducing to 3 years, and in the last year, only application-oriented courses such as School Experience and Teaching Practice should be included. In this direction, the teachers' opinions are as follows: "*One year internship is required to increase practical studies. Education and training should be 5 years.*" (T18); "*Instead of four years, three years of theoretical training should be provided, and in the fourth year a totally financial gain practising ,such as paid teachers, should be done.*"(T44). 34% (n = 20) of the teachers who expressed their opinions under the category "Opinions on the necessity of post graduate education" stated that the 4-years education period is sufficient to become a teacher but they thought that it is necessary for the teachers to continue their post graduate education programs for professional development. From teachers (T50) explained his/her opinion in this regard as follows:

"In my opinion the training period is adequate. However, in terms of self-improvement in the profession, teachers can study for master or doctorate."

Table 6 contains the opinions of participant teachers about the question "What are your views about the conditions for assignment to the teaching profession?"

Table 6: Teachers' Opinions about the Conditions of Assignment to Teaching Profession

Main categories	Sub-categories	Codes	f	%
Views on the Examination System	Views on The Interview Exam	The interview system should be removed.	33	34
		Interviews should be objective.	13	13
		Interviews should be conducted by domain experts.	11	12
	Views on The PPSE exam	Regulations should be made in the Public Personal Selection Examination (PPSE) which is applied at teacher appointments.	2	2
		Student quotas of faculties of education should be reduced.	12	13
		Assessment of prospective teacher should be done before the prospective graduates.	2	2
Views on The Status of Teachers to Be Assigned	Views on The Status of Staffed Teacher	Teacher assignments should be made on the basis of permanent teaching.	21	22
	Views on The Status of Contracted Teacher	Contract teacher status must be maintained at teacher assignments.	2	2

When Table 6 was examined, 34% (n = 33) of the participants within the category of "views on the examination system" (76%) indicated that the interview test which is applied in the teacher assignment, should be abolished and 25% of them indicated that the interview examinations should be applied in teacher assignment (13%, n=13), but these examinations should be objective and domain experts (12%, n=11) required for these exams. In this direction, the teachers' opinions are as follows: *"Interviewing is definitely wrong, because there is no need. Prospective teacher has already taken exam of PPSE. General ability, general knowledge, professional knowledge, content knowledge is tested. What is the purpose of the interview?"* (T17); *"The percentage of general knowledge should be lowered; the percentage of educational sciences and content knowledge examinations should be increased."* (T51). %13 (n=12) of the participant teachers within the category of "General views on the evaluation system" stated that the faculties of education student quotas should be reduced, while 2% (n = 2) per cent of them stated that the teacher candidates' evaluation activities should be applied before the candidates graduated, so each teacher candidate who graduated from faculty would take up a position directly.

According to Table 7, 24% of the participant teachers expressed their opinions within the category of "views on the status of teachers to be assigned" and 22% of them (n=21) stated that the assignment of teachers should only be in the position of permanent staff, and they had criticised contracted or paid teacher assignment system negatively. Teachers have stated that they find especially contractual teacher assignments as injustice, it is described as disrespect to teachers' personal rights, additionally, they pointed out that this system, which was introduced to provide

teacher employment in the eastern region, is not a correct system and that teachers have been incarcerated and aggrieved in a single school for 6 years and this situation is anomalous to family unity. From teachers (T7) clarified his/her opinion that "Become a teacher is so gruelling in Turkey. PPSE (have an exam with 12 lessons) + Interview (friend at court) + 6 year contract (no staff) etc... These misapplications cause unhappy teachers and they cause unhappy students. A teacher loses all his/her enthusiasm and energy without being assigned. These unfairness (contracted-permanent-paid) terms of assignment wears teachers out before they start to work. In addition, most of the contracted teachers have to separate from their partners, do not have family union, and have to work for 6 years in a place they do not want." Two of the teachers (n=2) stated that contrary to the above viewpoints, the contracted teacher status should be maintained in the teacher assignments. One of the teachers explained his opinion on this issue as follows: "The implementation of contracted teaching is the correct decision, because it is an application that is based on the obligation of the government. I hope to continue."(T16).

Table 7 contains the opinions of participant teachers about the question "What is your opinion about in-service training?"

Table 7: Teachers' Views on In-Service Training

Categories	Codes	f	%
Views on The Participation In The Trainings To Professional Development	Trainings provide professional development.	37	39
	Since the trainings are not carried out properly, professional development does not provide any contribution.	6	6
	The people who will provide training should be domain experts.	9	10
Views on The Quality of Training	Practice should be included in the trainings	7	7
	Education topics should be determined according to the interests and needs of teachers.	6	6
	People who will provide training should form a perception to teachers about the importance of education	2	2
Views on Teachers' Willingness To Participate in Trainings	Generally, the same teachers participate in the in-service trainings and this is made the other teachers unwilling	11	12
	Teachers' level of motivation for in-service training participation is low.	11	12
	Teachers do not participate in in-service trainings because they do not need professional development	1	1
Views on the Conditions of Participation to Trainings	There is a transportation problem where in-service training activities are carried out.	5	5

When Table 7 is examined, teachers express the most opinions with 45% has been categorized as "views on the participation in the training to professional improvement". While 39% (n=37) of teachers indicated positively that in-service training contributed to the professional development of the teachers, 6% (n=6) indicated that the training was excellent on paper but it is not carried out expediently because of the various difficulties in practicing and therefore it did not contribute to professional development. The views

of some of the teachers are as follows: *"In-service training is always necessary. It is beneficial for teachers to improve themselves professionally."*(T6); *"In my opinion in-service training is not constructive. On the desk everything is understandable, but when training is started, it cannot be implemented as it is in theory. I think that in-service trainings do not provide a professionally meaningful contribution, as practices do not satisfy teachers sufficiently."* (T37). 10% (n = 9) of the participant teachers within the category of "views on the quality of training" (n = 9) indicated that the people who will provide in-service trainings should be domain experts, because people who are not domain experts do not attach importance and pay attention training that the time wastes reading materials (slides, notes, etc.) containing information to be given. While one of the teachers (T4) explained his/her views on the quality of in-service training that *"In-service trainings are successful and quite beneficial in cities of western region ; in eastern provinces in-service training do not have any purpose, is inexperienced, just read the slides and aimed in order to know the Ministry that is done. Well-known educators in Turkey may be encouraged for training seminar in the east."* 12% (n=11) of the participant teachers indicated their opinions within the "views on teachers' willingness to participate in trainings "category that generally, the same teachers participate in the in-service trainings and this is made the other teachers unwilling to participate in trainings. In this regard one of the teachers (T33) clarified his/her ideas that *"Teachers should be encouraged the in-service trainings, trainings should not be in contemplation of for the sake of appearance, because in-service training is a renewal. However, teachers have sense of exhaustion and reluctance about these trainings. The reason for this is that certain people attend constantly and the others are obstructed."* One of the teachers in the same category (n = 1) criticises negatively his/her colleagues and stated that the teachers do not need for professional development and therefore they abstains from in-service training. 5% (n = 5) of the teachers stated within the category of "Views on the conditions of participation to trainings" that the participation rates in these trainings are not intended, because of the transportation problem in which the in-service training activities are carried out. One of the teachers' views on the issue is that: *"There may not be many attendances because of the distance of places where the in-service training activities are carried out, or problem of transportation."* (T1)

Table 8 contains the opinions of participant teachers about the question "What are your opinions about the teacher training system with pedagogical formation education certificate program?"

Table 8: Views about the Pedagogical Formation Education Certificate Program

Categories	Codes	f	%
Views on the Necessity of The Program	Since there is no teacher shortage in our country, there is no need for a teacher training system with certificate program.	13	32
	The certificate program should be opened by certain universities to the extent of the need for teacher.	6	15
	Teacher training with the certificate program is affecting negatively the development of education faculties.	3	7
	This program should be abolished by providing job opportunities to the students in the departments of the certificate program.	3	7

	The program is necessary to provide job opportunities for graduates of science and literature faculties.	2	5
Views on the Duration of the Program	The duration of the program is inadequate in terms of learning about the content of courses of professional knowledge.	8	20
	The duration of the program is insufficient in terms of gaining teaching skills.	3	7
Views on the Admission Conditions for the Program	In the conditions of admission to the program, the entrance score of the universities must be taken as a criterion.	3	7

When Table 8 was examined, 32% (n=13) of the teachers stated within the category of "Views on the necessity of the program" that there is not teacher shortage and even the number of unassigned teachers are many in number and therefore teacher training system with the certificate program are not needed. One of the teachers (T56) *"I think that there are enough teachers who graduated from the faculty of education. Their employment should be provided primarily."* the other one is (T35) *"It is an implementation to be made teacher everybody and so-called having a profession. There is a teacher who is not already assigned enough. Their employment must be provided firstly."* had expressed their negative views on the certificate program. 15% of the teachers (n = 6) stated that certificate programs are necessary to meet teacher deficit for some departments but these programs must be opened by certain universities to according to the need of the teacher. From teachers (T26) *"It should not be distributed to everyone like distributing bread."*; additionally (T22) *"It should be given to the required branches-not all of them- by the big universities to train teachers as needed."* explained their opinions.

20% of the teachers (n=8) stated within the category of "Views on the duration of the program" that their certificate programs are opened in a very short period of time, and this period is not sufficient for understanding and internalizing the content of teaching profession information courses at the desired level, and they think the period should be extended. From teachers (T8) opined that *"It is an implementation which gives insufficient information because of the narrowness of period of pedagogical formation and short duration of its education."* %7 of participant teachers (n=3) opined on the admission conditions for the program and they expressed that entrance score to university must be a criteria on the condition of application and admission to the program, the entry scores who are close to the entry scores to the faculty of education should be admitted to the program, otherwise they would be unfair to the teacher candidates who are studying and graduating from faculty of education. One of the teachers stated his opinion as follows: *"Nonsense! How can a human being who enter with a low score be given such a right and put it on the same level as graduate from the faculty of education. To stipulate! Therefore students whose scores are equivalent to the faculty of education can apply."* (T47)

4. Conclusion, Discussion, Recommendations

As a result of this study which scrutinises the teacher training system in Turkey with the teachers' opinions, it has been detected that teachers who participate in the research, have negative opinions on teacher training system in Turkey. Participant teachers

primarily criticized our teacher training policy, they referred MEB as the first source of the problems in the teacher training system in our country, and they stated MEB has no national teacher training policy and these policies are shaped according to the government reshuffle. Çelikten, Şanal and Yeni (2005) indicated in their studies that, similar to results of this study, the teaching profession is affected immediately from the implementation of government reshuffle of Turkey, even if the political powers change, the government needs to have a national policy on teacher training and assignments, as long as this policy does not exist, the teaching profession cannot reach the desired and deserved status. In addition, participant teachers expressed that, as a result of this research, they saw MEB as responsible to teacher recruitment, due to the fact that the MEB is not sufficiently connected with Board of Higher Education (YÖK) in Turkey, non-need teacher is trained, and therefore the number of unemployed teachers is increasing every year.

In the study conducted by Atanur-Başkan (2001), it is stated that there is not a healthy cooperation and coordination between the institutions responsible for teacher training and the competent institution for teacher employment, and thus the supply-demand balance in teacher employment cannot be provided. Essentially, the basic question to be answered about teacher education is "*What is the vision and mission of a contemporary teacher who will work in the conditions of our country and how does a teacher with this vision and mission grow in the system?*" This question is not only a question that MEB or YÖK will look for an answer. MEB, YÖK, faculties of education, teachers, students, parents, parent-teacher association, unions and the other educators should come together with representatives of the people and institutions involved and should form a national teacher training policy by finding answers to these questions which are exit points. Educating teachers is not the one and only thing; the other matter is also teacher employment. As stated in Aydin, Sarier, Uysal, Aydoğdu-Özoğlu and Özer (2014), although teacher employment is a fact which should be evaluated within the supply and demand balance as it is in every area, the supply and demand balance mentioned today cannot be established sufficiently, while teacher candidates are graduated, the need for teachers is also emerging in some areas. This indicates that there is no co-operation between YÖK-MEB among the institutions that guide education policies. Once a national teacher training policy has been established, an organic link between YÖK and MEB on teacher training and employment has to be established and the employment problem should be eliminated.

As a result of this research, some of the teachers who participated in the research stated their views on teacher training policies of YÖK. However, when these views are considered, it appears that the teachers are more concerned with the negative criticisms of teacher education graduate curricula. It was determined that 19% of the teachers thought that the courses were mostly theoretically processed during the undergraduate education period. Same results were found in the third sub-problem of the research, the teachers stated that the theoretical and practical balance of the courses in the undergraduate curriculum has not been sufficiently established and therefore the curricula should be revised. The imbalance between theory and practice, or more

appropriately the gap between knowledge and practice, implies the difficulty of transforming knowledge into actions that are consistent with this knowledge (Pfeffer & Sutton, 2000, p.4). The challenges faced by teachers in the process of action transformation can negatively affect their self-efficacy in making classroom practices, and the teaching-learning environment will probably go beyond the process in which teachers are in the process of transferring theoretical knowledge. When literature is examined, it is seen that in many researches, university-based teacher education programs give more theoretical information and the implementation studies are not done sufficiently (Orhan, 2017; Özmen & Özdemir, 2016; Akhan, 2015; Lynch & Yeigh, 2013; Baştürk, 2011; Kuran & Aktaş, 2010; Lynch & Smith, 2010; Gök & Erdoğan, 2009; Gordon & O'Brien, 2006; Beck & Kosnik, 2002; Daniel, 2004; Tom, 1997, p.48). Therefore, it can be said that this problem is a general problem of teacher training programs. The teaching-learning processes of the lessons should be rearranged in such a way that prospective teachers will be able to conduct practical work that will help them gain teaching skills. In this regard, YÖK may prepare sample guide books on how to implement classroom practices in courses for the commissions and instructors to be formed. In these guide books, information about the achievements of the lessons, contents, teaching-learning processes and measurement-evaluation studies may be involved. Sample practice activities can be set for courses that are suitable for classroom practice. In this way, it is possible for instructors to feel more secure about being able to practice in class. In addition, some of the teachers who participated in the survey (19%) found that the lessons of School Experience and Teaching Practice were inadequate and should be increased. Some of the participant teachers (15%; n=12) stated that the weekly application hours of the School Experience and Teaching Practice courses should be increased. These lessons are important in terms of how the prospective teachers better understand the importance of the theoretical knowledge they receive in the pre-service period and how they can be used where they are used in the teaching process. As Hammond pointed out (2010), it is impossible for prospective teachers to acquire teaching skills by asking them to imagine situations they have never seen before. These lessons provide the teacher candidates with the opportunity to experience rather than imagine what they have never seen. In addition, these lessons also allow prospective teachers to become aware of whether they are suitable for the teaching profession, to gain experience in the profession, and to develop stronger interpersonal relationships (Güllü & Temel, 2016; LaMaster, 2001). The researches carried out are those of the teacher candidates who take these courses; have developed positive professional perceptions and have gained professional experience. (Sürücü, Ünal & Yıldırım, 2017, Avcı & İbret, 2016, Msangya, Mkoma & Yihuan, 2016, Ekinci, Tican-Başaran, 2015, Özay-Köse, 2014, Değirmençay & Kasap, 2013; Christenson & Barney, 2011, Hascher, Cocard & Moser, 2004, Becit, Kurt & Kabakçı, 2009). Therefore, it is proposed to increase the credits of these courses, which are provided by the application of the theoretical knowledge which forms the basis of the teaching to the teacher candidates.

As a result of the survey, it was determined that the majority of the participating teachers (99%) stated that the entrance conditions to the faculties of education should be

revised. It is stated that 77% of the teachers must apply the graduated examination system to the faculties of education and the candidates who are placed in the faculties of education according to the results of the central examination; it has been determined that tests such as oral and written tests, personality tests, occupational interest tests, teacher proficiency tests, psychological tests, values and mental health tests should be applied. Teachers' character and professional competence are the most important factors influencing the quality of education and indirectly national development (Kumar & Ratnalikar, 2005). So, it is necessary to carry out studies to ensure that people who are professionally committed to the teaching profession and have the qualifications to carry out this profession become teachers. university entrance examinations are conducted centrally in Turkey every year as a result of an increase in the number of individuals who apply for these exams, students with multiple choice questions only operates as a system that screening based on cognitive development. However, to be a teacher, besides cognitive development, there is also a need for features such as interest in the profession, affective characteristics such as attitude, self-expression, basic personality in which the teaching profession can run, psychological structure and mental health. Similar issues were also mentioned in the report "Teacher Strategy Document" (2017), which was published by the General Directorate of Teacher Training and Development of MEB. It has been stated that a system based on multiple data sources should be applied to the teaching profession, in which the selection process must be redesigned in multi-stage and with the criteria set forth, taking into account the psychomotor and affective skills of the candidates at the beginning of the profession. Also, as a result of this research, 17% of the teachers stated that they should conduct their job orientation studies under the category of opinions on revising the entrance conditions to the faculties of education. 10% of the participants (n=9) suggested that the work should be done at the high school level and that the students who can carry out the teaching profession could be determined and directed to the faculties of education during the high school education. During the four-year high school education process, it is possible for the students, who are judged by the board decision that they can observe the teaching profession by observation by the teachers in different branches, to be directed to the faculties of education, to increase the quality of the student profile in the faculty. One of the teachers in the same category (n=1) suggested that the choice of parents should be made in upper classes according to the comments of the teacher candidates and the directions of the instructors at the end of the one or several years basic education period to be taken in the faculty rather than making preferences in the entrance to the faculties of education. A similar view is stated within the scope of MEB Teacher Strategy Document (2017) and it is stated that in certain areas with teacher education, the program preference is aimed to create a system that can be done after entering the faculty. Such a system will allow prospective teachers to experience a certain amount of time in the field to determine the level of interest in the discipline which is higher, so teacher candidates will be able to branch out in areas of high interest and attitude.

As a result of the research, it was determined that 90% of the participating teachers indicated that their opinions about teaching programs applied in faculties of education were negative and that the contents of the programs and teaching-learning processes had to be revised. It was found that 14% of the teachers thought that the lessons should be added to the program. The majority of the teachers who expressed their views in this direction stated that all of the university and internship trainings were in the provincial centers, but that the first appointment places were generally village schools. Teachers clarified their own thoughts in faculties about village life schools and village schools, indicating that they have not had any information about the difficulties of school life in the rural areas, the problems waiting for teachers in the village and the possible solutions of these problems or about the conditions of village schools and thus have serious problems in adapting to village schools and village life. They should be added to the course. Sidekli, Coşkun and Aydın (2015) stated that the fact that the teacher candidates did not prepare them for the fact that they were village teachers at the city centre where the courses of teaching practice were taught during their undergraduate studies and that they could not adapt to the village environment when they were assigned villagers. There is a lesson called "Teaching in Combined Classes" which is theoretically processed for 2 hours a week in the 8th semester within the scope of knowledge courses in the current Class Teaching Undergraduate Teaching Program. It is possible to make a study to meet the needs of the teachers by expanding the scope of this course in the classroom teacher program and putting an elective course in the general culture area for the living conditions in the rural areas and the conditions of the schools in the undergraduate curriculum of the candidate teachers who will be working in secondary education. In addition, 9% of the participating teachers in this sub-problem indicated their views on the applicants of the programs. Teachers criticized the educators that gave training in faculties of education because they were not adequately equipped in their field of expertise and majority of them had no teaching experience and this situation prevented the teaching programs applied at faculties from achieving the goals. Similarly, in the study conducted by Aksu, Çivitçi & Duy (2008), it was concluded that some of the higher education students who participated in the research stated that they did not find the instructors sufficiently equipped in the areas they were teaching. In the study carried out by Erginer, Erginer & Bedir (2009), it has been determined that the academic origins of some of the teaching staff employed in the faculties of education are not related to teacher education (science-literacy faculties, fine arts faculties, engineering faculties, economics and management faculties). This situation also shows that teacher trainers working in faculties of education need to get education about the importance of teacher training, teacher competencies, teaching methods and techniques, planning of teaching process, instructional design, etc. It is doubtful how qualified information will be presented to the prospective teachers to be trained by an educator who is not yet qualified and knowledgeable in these matters. As Korthagen, Loughran & Lunenberg (2005) point out, teacher trainers do not only support students' learning during the teaching-learning process, but they also have the task of modeling with pupils. In this respect,

teacher educators differ from educators educating medical doctors. Doctors do not act like a role model in the teaching process, but the teacher teaches the educators to teach their students with or without awareness. Therefore, it is suggested that the revision studies for our teacher training system should start from faculties of education to prevent any possible problems. Pedagogical knowledge should be given to the faculty members whose pedagogical knowledge is insufficient or who have not reached this knowledge at first, and then the arrangements for the selection of the instructors to train the teachers should be done. The fact that they have fulfilled the teaching profession for a certain period of time should be regarded as a basic criterion for their ability to function as educational faculties.

As a result of the research, it was found that some of the teachers (34%) stated that the 4-year-education-period was sufficient to be a teacher and that the teachers were able to do post-graduate education for professional development when the opinions about the education-training periods applied in faculties of education were examined. Considering the applications in the advanced European countries in terms of teacher training, it seems that most of these countries require 4 or 5 years of undergraduate education in order to start the profession in the preschool, primary and secondary schools, and for the students who want to teach at the high school level, it is necessary to have graduate degree (Eurydice, 2013). In Finland, which is on the agenda to provide high quality education and training opportunities for its students, no one is able to teach without graduation at any level (Kazu & Aşkın, 2011). Considering the quality problems in teacher education in our country, it may be necessary to put graduate condition for some branches taking into consideration the current teacher training period on the basis of the branches again with the mutual talks between MEB and YÖK.

As a result of the survey, it was determined that the opinions of the participating teachers about the conditions of appointment to the teaching profession were generally collected under two views; abolishment of interview system (34%) and maintenance of the interview system objectively (13%) and by field specialists (12%). Some of the participating teachers expressed the view that candidate teachers should not be tested again with interview system because they are already tested in the areas of the general talent-general culture, field knowledges, and craft knowledge levels with Public Personnel Selection Examination (PPSE). Others stated that the teacher candidates who completed the undergraduate education process did not qualify the general qualifications of the teaching profession in the desired qualities and that the regulations should be made in order to meet the requirements such as making the interview system necessary but also ensuring objectivity and juries specialities. Yılmaz (2016); in the work done by Şahan (2016), the teacher candidates stated that it is necessary to carry out the interview exam as well as Public Personnel Selection Examination the in the process of appointment to the teaching profession. 22% of the surveyed teachers stated that teacher appointments should only be in the position of permanent teaching, and that the contracted teaching status would lead to unfair practices among the teachers. Teachers also wondered that contracted teachers are not different from the existing staff

members in terms of the way they are taught and the qualifications of the teachers but that the differences in the personal rights of the staff are unfair to the teachers and that this will negatively affect the teachers' dignity of the profession and the willingness to realize the goals of the school and the school they bring. It is likely that it is possible for teachers to begin to move away from school and school to achieve their physical and emotional goals when they feel that inequality or injustice in any context is felt when teachers compare themselves to their colleagues in the rapporteur of "Teacher's Eyes Teaching Profession" (2014) conducted by Tedmem and this motivation it will be possible to reduce the number of students to achieve the objectives of the school, or even to move away from adoption. The realization of school objectives is one of the important steps in achieving the goals of national education. The lack of motivation in teachers' involvement in this step will directly affect the achievement of the goals of national education and will result in the achievement of the educational goals of the country. Therefore, in the regulations to be made in our teacher training system, the opinions of the teachers regarding the contracted teaching status should be taken into consideration and the teachers' loyalty to the teachers should be strengthened by abolishing this status which will lead to separation between the teachers.

As a result of the research, 39% of participating teachers declare positive in the point of in-service training contributing to professional development, 6% of them think that in-service training is done only to be done in contrary to increase the professional development of teachers and to equip them with new knowledge and skills. It is determined that they declare a negative opinion at the point where they do not provide the development solid. In parallel with the results of this research, it was found out that the opinions of the teachers and administrators participating in the research on the in-service training programs were generally negative and that they were not sufficiently satisfied with the in-service training activities in the results of the research conducted by Uçar & İpek (2006) and Aydoğan (2002). Guskey (1986) states that students cannot attain the desired qualities for the purposes of in-service training conducted with the aim of increasing the achievement levels and obtaining information about new teaching strategies. Teachers who expressed the view that the quality of in-service training should be increased, stated that the subjects of education should be determined according to the interests and needs of the teachers and that the persons who will give education should be field experts and practical studies should be given in the trainings. It is stated that in-service training activities are ineffective due to the fact that the in-service training activities are carried out without considering the branch and training needs (Sıcak & Parmaksız, 2016; Bümen, Ateş, Çakar, Ural & Acar, 2012; Gökyer, 2012), that the personnel who gives training are not specialists (Özen, 2006; Bozkurt et al, 2012) and that the practices are less or inadequate (Huong & Yeo 2016; Hung, 2016; Sıcak & Parmaksız, 2016; Özen, 2006). Moreover, it was seen that the teachers who participated in the survey also expressed their opinion that the teachers were reluctant to participate in the in-service training. 12% of teachers reported that they were reluctant to participate in in-service training by claiming that the same teachers were generally regarded as participants in the province, so this situation made the teachers

who applied for the training and couldn't accepted reluctant. Therefore, in-service training studies should be carried out in order to ensure that each teacher can benefit equally, taking into consideration the branches and needs of the in-service training. Needs analysis studies should be carried out in the determination of the training topics and information should be provided to the teachers about the need for more time allocated to trainings and number of practical exercises should be increased.

In the survey, it is pointed that the views of teachers who are related to teacher training with pedagogical formation are generally negative. Teachers stated that this system is not needed because there is no teacher vacancy in our country, the system has blown up the development of faculties of education and the system should be terminated by recognizing job opportunities for the students. In addition, some of the teachers (15%) stated that the system of teacher training with certificate program should be given by certain universities for departments that are suitable for teachers. In the study carried out by Yılmaz & Altinkurt (2011), it was determined that some of the prospective teachers who participated in the research criticized in negative the evaluation of graduates of science and literature faculties as teachers rather than the faculty of education, and that this was not a correct application. Participating teachers also expressed their views on the duration of the pedagogical formation training certificate program and the conditions of the program acceptance, and stated that the overall duration of the program was generally inadequate and that teaching competencies could not be acquired in a short period of time. Teachers who stated that the conditions of acceptance of the program should also be regulated explained that candidates applying for the program should take university entrance scores into consideration and candidates whose scores are close to the entry points of the faculties of education should be accepted as a program. In the study carried out by Köse (2017), academicians participating in the research criticized in negative the possibility of being a teacher through pedagogical formation education. The academicians say that the pedagogical formation of the teacher training is compressed and that the teacher training is not intimidated and the students with high scores in faculties of education are being downtrodden due to the pedagogical formation and the number of the teacher candidates who are more than the current situation and waiting for appointment is increased by pedagogical formation, that this constitutes a problem for the country as well, and that teaching qualifications and competences cannot be gained by those who continue the program through pedagogical formation. In the work of Demirbaş & Kırbaç (2016), it was determined that the pedagogical formation students stated that the program period was short and inadequate because of the program being compressed, and that the time and conditions of the program had to be adjusted well in order to train more qualified. Bell, Cihak, & Judge (2010) stated that the length of teacher training programs should be long enough to give teacher candidates sufficient qualifications. Based on these results, it is suggested that the pedagogical formation program should be given by some universities in the areas required, and the duration of the training should be extended in order to increase the quality of the education.

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